

MSU
TOOLBOX
DIALOGUE
INITIATIVE

CONTENTS

Overview	1
Theory Behind the Toolbox.....	3
Evaluation Approach & Design	4
Data Collection.....	5
Findings	12
Conclusions	24
References	26
Appendix A.....	27
Appendix B.....	33
Appendix C.....	34
Appendix D.....	36
Appendix E	38
Appendix F	40

OVERVIEW

The Toolbox Dialogue Initiative (TDI) at Michigan State University (MSU) commissioned the Evaluation Center (EC) at Western Michigan University to conduct a collaborative, summative evaluation of its Toolbox workshops. The primary purpose of the evaluation is to determine the impact of TDI's workshops on individual workshop participants. It includes an assessment of TDI's ability to increase the communicative and collaborative capacity of workshop participants, as measured by their self-expressed attitudes towards research, mutual understanding, and team cohesion. In turn, impacts on attitudes and behaviors related to research are theorized by TDI to improve research productivity in cross-disciplinary and collaborative settings.

The evaluation structure is based on the Kirkpatrick Model (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2006), which looks at four levels of training outcomes. Because this examination of TDI workshops is retrospective and summative, the evaluation is largely objectives-based and descriptive in nature. The evaluation took place between April and September 2017, and is focused on workshop sessions that occurred during roughly the previous three years.

WHAT IS THE TOOLBOX DIALOGUE INITIATIVE?

TDI was originally created with support from the National Science Foundation (NSF) as an initiative intended to facilitate communication in cross-disciplinary research and practice. Rooted in philosophical analysis, the Toolbox approach brings together cross-disciplinary collaborators to engage in a structured dialogue about their research assumptions. The intent of the process is to develop self-awareness, and mutual understanding, as well as supplying cross-disciplinary research (CDR) collaborators with the foundation needed for effective collaborative research and practice.

During each Toolbox workshop, members of a collaborative research or practice team gather to discuss aspects of their research or professional worldviews through completion and discussion of the Toolbox instrument. This instrument is a survey comprising potentially divisive prompts that articulate normative assumptions. Prompts are organized into modules that correspond to important dimensions of a collaborative project (e.g., values, methodology, confirmation, modeling). Participants indicate their level of agreement with each prompt. Responses to these prompts are then discussed among the group during a facilitated dialogue that lasts up to two hours. Through these discussions, it is hoped that participants can discover surprising differences and similarities, which can lead to recognition, communication, negotiation, compromise, and mutual understanding among the participants. At the close of a workshop, participants complete the Toolbox instrument again, which can help to highlight shifts in thinking or attitude, as well as provide a final opportunity for reflection.

In addition to the dialogue, some groups also participant in a co-creative activity concerning their current research project. These activities are intended to bring the group together around common activities related to their own research projects or collaborative efforts.

Within several weeks of participation in the Toolbox workshop, participants are asked to complete a post-workshop questionnaire that solicits open-ended reactions to the introspective, interactive, and evaluative effects of the Toolbox experience. The TDI staff summarizes workshop findings and experiences in a final report, which is given to the "leader" of the workshop group and participants. A visual representation of the theory and operation of TDI workshop is presented in Figure 1.

Since the program’s inception, TDI staff has conducted workshops with research groups that operate in a wide variety of domains, including academic science, community resiliency, and regional sustainability. At the time of the evaluation, there have been over 200 workshops conducted internationally and over 1,300 individuals have participated in the Toolbox workshops.

Figure 1. Toolbox Dialogue Initiative Workshop Model

THEORY BEHIND THE TOOLBOX

Today, there is worldwide recognition that many of society's major problems can no longer be addressed appropriately within the confines of individual disciplines (Royal Society 1996; OECD 1998). It has been further recognized that collaborative, cross-disciplinary research (CDR) is a required activity and is increasingly part of a trend toward real world problem-solving (Crow 2010). However, it is duly noted that challenges and obstacles exist when trying to conduct cross-disciplinary research, some of which are related to conceptual and methodological differences existing between knowledge domains. Meeting this challenge requires dramatically changing how researchers think, communicate, and apply new knowledge within collaborative research projects. Essential to overcoming the barriers to CDR is the researchers' ability to effectively communicate across disciplines. Without such communication, the degree to which it is necessary to combine disciplines becomes comprised (Winowiecki et al. 2011).

Despite the increasing need to initiate collaborative projects and the increase in funding opportunities that encourage collaboration, practical approaches to enhancing communication and collaboration have emerged slowly. The fundamental premise behind the Toolbox approach is to enable teams of researchers to identify and solve project-level challenges through structured group communication. The Toolbox approach consists of two parts, the Toolbox workshop and the Toolbox instrument. Lightly facilitated dialogue, prompted by the Toolbox instrument, is intended to enhance cross-disciplinary communication and integration, and increase mutual understanding through the revelation of various research worldviews (e.g., background assumptions, methodological assumptions); which is crucial to CDR success (i.e., effective collaborating in research and practice) (Eigenbrode et al. 2007).

EVALUATION APPROACH & DESIGN

The evaluation approach seeks to answer the following primary evaluation question:

What are the short- and long-term impacts of Toolbox workshops on individual participants, workshop groups, organizations, and beyond?

Due to the nature of the program and the fact that it has been in operation for some time, the focus of the evaluation is summative, objectives-based, and descriptive in nature. Additionally, TDI is unique in that it addresses a topic area—research collaboration—that has generally not been targeted by other similar programs. Therefore, the evaluation does not utilize a comparative approach; it does not seek to measure the performance of individuals against a random or matched comparison group, nor does it assess the outcomes of the program relative to other programs. Instead, this evaluation has focused on collecting and measuring evidence on the progress of participants toward larger programmatic goals, which are centered around the principles of cross-disciplinary collaboration.

The evaluation design, as well as the reporting of results, utilize the framework of the well-known Kirkpatrick Model to look at four levels of outcomes, namely:

REACTION: how participants react to the workshop; similar to customer satisfaction

LEARNING: measurement of what participants learned during the workshop

BEHAVIOR: represents whether or not participants changed their behavior in expected ways after the workshop

RESULTS: measurement of broad outcomes as related to project goals

Evidence of performance on outcomes within each of these levels was collected through several means, including observation of a Toolbox workshop; program records and documents; a survey of past participants; and interviews with a small set of participants.

DATA COLLECTION

GENERAL AND FORMATIVE OBSERVATIONS

Two activities conducted during the early stages of the evaluation included a review of documents and literature on TDI and the observation of a Toolbox workshop session conducted at MSU. Although these activities were not intended to be used in the summative assessment of TDI, they did provide several findings of importance to the ongoing refinement of the program, as well as planning for a possible long-term internal evaluation.

REVIEW OF DOCUMENTS AND LITERATURE

An initial review of documents revealed that TDI staff has conducted approximately 226 workshops with 1,330 participants. Due to the fact that many of the initial TDI workshops were classified as preliminary and often used to inform future workshops, data used for evaluative purposes were drawn from workshops 99 through 225 (n=126). As seen in Figure 2, a majority of TDI workshops conducted during the analysis period were done pro-bono (n=78). There were 35 workshops conducted as a one-time opportunity or single case, while 13 workshops have been conducted as on-going (i.e., on a long-term basis).

61% of workshops were provided through pro bono contracts.

Pro Bono	Single	Long-Term
78	35	13

Figure 2. Contract Type

As illustrated in Figure 3, the groups who attend workshops are at various stages of collaboration. Around one-fourth of the groups participating in the workshops have been working on projects for four or more years (n=31) and approximately one fifth of the groups had recently received funding for their collaborative project (n=27). Most of the remaining groups' projects were classified as exploratory, or were within their second or third year. Nineteen percent of workshops had no reported point in time for the group. Additionally, there was one workshop conducted during the first year and one during grant-writing phase.

24% of workshops were conducted in or after year four. 21% of projects conducted workshops after just being funded.

Figure 3. Duration of participant projects at time of workshop (n = 126)

As seen in Figure 4, the most common reason reported for groups attending a Toolbox workshop was for educational and training s (n=63). While there were several groups whose main focus was research (n=32), there were other groups whose purpose was collaborating for advocacy and policy (n=15).

50% of the workshops purposes were for Education and training.

Figure 4. Purpose of Workshop Group (n = 126)

TDI's documentation also provided a classification of the objective of each workshop. It was found that a majority of the workshops had more than one objective. Below is a list of workshop objectives as described by the TDI staff.

- Demo
- Encourage critical reflection and analysis
- Foster new collaborations
- Reflect on previous process
- Identify relevant stakeholders
- Identify group and individual values & priorities
- Explore power dynamics within the group
- Define mission, vision, and goals
- Develop next steps for group action
- Build research capacity

TDI's cross-disciplinary discussion in the workshops is prompted by completion of a Toolbox instrument. Prompts in the instrument are organized into modules that correspond to important dimensions of a collaborative, cross-disciplinary project. As seen in Figure 5, most workshops used an existing Toolbox instrument, while 40% used an instrument that was customized to fit the needs of the participating group. Other Toolbox instruments included either hybrid or "mash-up" versions of other instruments.

Figure 5. Instrument Type

WORKSHOP OBSERVATION

On March 22, 2017, the evaluation team visited the MSU campus to meet with the TDI team and observe a Toolbox workshop. Experiencing a Toolbox workshop provided the evaluation team with firsthand experience, as well as alerting the team to how the Toolbox instrument was used in practice. Although the modules completed by Toolbox participants before and at the end of the workshops were originally envisioned as pre- and post-test instruments, the observation made it clear that the actual use of the results was to stimulate group discussion. Participants are asked to complete the module in an online app, which allows the facilitators to quickly compile and present the results. These results were then used to highlight differences in perspectives and serve as a starting point for group discussion.

Based on the workshop observation, it was decided that the data from the modules completed at the beginning and end of each Toolbox should not be used in the evaluation. Although the items in the module use standard scale scores that could theoretically be compared, the timeframe between completing the pre and post modules was very short. Furthermore, the design and usage of the modules suggested that any change in the scale scores would not reflect an interpretable gain in knowledge or change in belief. This is partially due to the fact that TDI does not have a goal of pushing participants to a certain or specific point of understanding, but instead focuses on helping participants to become aware of different beliefs or understandings held by other team members.

PARTICIPANT SURVEY

Most of the findings discussed in this section are derived from the results of a survey of former Toolbox participants. The survey¹ was conducted by first identifying all individuals in TDI's database who had both: a) completed a Toolbox workshop session during the previous three-years, and b) indicated a willingness to participate in Toolbox-related research by providing a valid email address and marking the appropriate checkbox on their sign-in form. Overall, this resulted in a list of 369 individuals, which was further reduced to 299 by removing invalid, duplicative, or inactive email addresses. The list of participants was sent an invitation to complete the online survey on July 5, 2017. As many as seven follow-up reminders were sent to those who did not respond by completing the survey or opting out.

A total of 92 individuals responded to the survey by the time it was closed to responses on August 18, 2017. However, some respondents either only opened the survey or did not proceed beyond the first question on eligibility, resulting in a final total of 73 who provided at least a partial valid survey response. The final overall response rate was 24 percent, which is lower than hoped but not unheard of for a survey conducted without incentives.

Figure 6 presents the demographic characteristics of the Toolbox participants who responded to the survey. Demographic questions were presented at the end of the survey and not all respondent completed the survey in its entirety. Overall there were 63 respondents who completed the demographics portion of the survey. As a group, the respondents are mostly between the ages of 25 and 54, majority female, and predominantly White.

¹ Survey questions can be seen in Appendix A.

AGE GROUP

GENDER

RACE AND ETHNICITY

Figure 6. Age, gender, and race of survey respondents (n = 63)

Survey respondents were asked about the organization that they work for and their professional role. Table 1 shows the primary professional role indicated by respondents. As seen in the table, professional roles indicated by respondents were mainly academic (n=38, 60%) in nature (i.e. either faculty, professor, or student).

Table 1. Professional role of survey participants

Occupation or Role	Count (n = 63)	Percentage
Academic (faculty/professor)	20	32%
Student	18	28%
Scientist or researcher	13	21%
Administration (management)	5	8%
Other (responses below)	7	11%
Community Organizer		
Consultant		
Development Professional		
Learning Specialist		
Marketing and Outreach Specialist		
Professional service provider		

Figure 7 summarizes the types of organizations where the respondents work and conduct research. In general, the responses to these questions reflect an audience drawn largely from academic institutions and research labs.

78% College or University

11% Non-profit organization

8% Government Agency

3% Business / Private Industry

Figure 7. Primary work or research environment of survey participants

TELEPHONE INTERVIEWS

The evaluation team made multiple attempts to collect qualitative data from former TDI participants, with limited success. Initially, the EC worked with TDI to identify participants from organizations located in the greater-Lansing area. Those nearby former participants were invited to attend a lunch focus group session at the Kellogg Center on the MSU campus. Unfortunately, despite trying several different dates there were not enough willing respondents to create a focus group of appropriate size. Because the majority of the people contacted were faculty or students who may not have been from MSU or Michigan, the difficulty in getting enough respondents may have been a result of the time of year as many faculty and students are not on campus in the summer months.

Alternate methods of collecting qualitative feedback on the TDI workshops were also pursued by the evaluation team. After the in-person focus groups received an insufficient response, the TDI staff then helped to identify a larger random selection of participants who were invited to participate in a virtual online focus group. However, the response was still not sufficient to fill an 8-12 person focus group. Finally, individuals who had responded affirmatively to the focus group invitations, as well as another randomly selected group of 30 former participants, were asked to participate in an individual phone interview during September 2017. In total, only two telephone interviews were conducted. Although the amount of data collected through these few interviews was not sufficient to draw significant conclusions regarding Toolbox outcomes, relevant comments and ideas derived from these discussions are mentioned in the conclusions section.

FINDINGS

This following section presents evaluation findings, which are organized around the four hierarchical levels of TDI outcomes. These findings are primarily derived from the survey of former participants; however, also included are supplemental findings taken from interviews with participants, as well as a review of TDI documents and internal data.

REACTION

The survey included 16 individual items that measured the participants' reaction to the Toolbox workshops. Survey respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with each item in order to provide feedback on what aspects of the Toolbox experience they liked or did not like, and how they believed their Toolbox group responded.

As shown in Figure 8, the responses of former participants indicated mostly positive feelings regarding the Toolbox experience. For example, large majorities agreed or strongly agreed that the workshop helped start conversations, identified research worldviews, and helped them have a better understanding of how others think about research. Importantly, over 80% also agreed that they enjoyed the workshop and felt that it was a good use of their time.

In no instance did a majority of respondents indicate a negative reaction (i.e. that they disagreed or strongly disagreed with a positive statement about the Toolbox experience). However, it is also worth noting that not all reactions were positive and there did appear to be significant problem areas among the Reaction items. In particular, more than one-third of respondents disagreed that the Toolbox workshop had improved their attitude toward team communication or enhanced collaboration amongst their group. One quarter of respondents also disagreed that the Toolbox had built a sense of community among their group. Additionally, nearly 18% disagreed that the Toolbox workshop was a good use of their time; although a minority, this still represents a sizable portion of respondents indicating that they had an experience that they did not feel was useful (Figure 8).

Participant agreement ratings on reaction items.

Figure 8. Agreement ratings on Reaction items

In addition to being asked questions intended to gauge reaction to the general Toolbox experience, respondents were also asked if they had participated in a group activity (often called a co-creation activity) as part of their workshop. Not all workshops conducted over the past three years included a group activity; therefore, only survey respondents who indicated that they remembered participating in a group activity were presented with questions about this aspect of the Toolbox.

Figure 9 summarizes participants' reactions to the group activity. A majority of the respondents who indicated they had been through the group activity either agreed or strongly agreed that it improved communication and collaboration in the group. Most respondents also found the activity to be a good use of their time. However, around a third of respondents did not feel that the activity improved collaboration or communication.

Participant agreement ratings on the group activity.

Figure 9. Agreement ratings on the group activity (n = 23)

GENERAL INSIGHTS AND COMMENTS

In addition to the specific questions regarding Reaction, the survey also asked two open-ended questions: one about insights gained during the experience and another asking respondents to share any final thoughts about their experience participating in the Toolbox workshop. Twenty-nine respondents provided comments concerning insights, while sixteen provided general comments on their Toolbox experience. While the comments on these two open-ended questions were not limited in scope to any single aspect of the workshop experience, they are presented here in the Reaction section since many of the responses focus on participant satisfaction (or dissatisfaction), as well as observations on the value of the program, and suggestions for improving the workshop experience. A listing of the comments provided by participants is provided in Appendix E and F.²

The key finding from these two questions is that the insights and experiences of past Toolbox experiences are highly mixed. Although there were many specific insights and general positive statements, such as “keep up the good work” shared by participants, there were also targeted criticisms that the TDI staff may wish to consider when developing future sessions.

Examples of common insights gained from participating in the Toolbox included: 1) recognizing differences in ideas and assumptions of individuals through open communication, 2) open dialogue can provide a means to establishing commonalities in vocabulary and language use, and 3) it is critical to understand others when collaborating on projects. The insight comments suggest that most participants felt that they learned something about the need for collaboration and the differences in worldview that can impact cross-disciplinary work. However, some respondents also indicated that the insights were either not very strong or not transferable to their own research activities. Examples include statements such as “I didn’t really gain any substantive insights” and “the Toolbox identified our differences, but made no effort to bridge those differences.”

Although the comments provided are not necessarily representative of the average participant experience, they do illustrate some unexpected strengths and weaknesses of the Toolbox workshops. The following list summarizes and highlights these observations.

² Note that the list of comments in the appendix has been edited to remove non-response comments (e.g. “none” or “no”); to remove comments related to technical aspects of the survey; to prevent potentially identifying information; and to fix obvious typos.

- Stopping bad collaborations is also a potentially valuable outcome
- Extroverted or aggressive participants sometimes dominate conversations during the workshops, to the detriment of others
- There may be generational divides in scientific worldview and communication style
- Memories of the workshops are short; participants desire any follow-up to occur shortly after completing the workshop

LEARNING

The survey included seven individual quantitative items along with three open-ended questions that addressed the learning of TDI participants. Some of the survey items focused on Learning are similar to the Reaction items in that they ask respondents to indicate their agreement or disagreement with statements regarding their individual Toolbox experience. However, respondents were also asked to rate their overall effectiveness of the workshop as a way of learning how to communicate with others, work with a cross-disciplinary group, and understand how others conduct research. In general, the results from these survey items showed that respondents were mixed regarding what they felt had been learned during the Toolbox workshop.

Although a majority disagreed that the workshop had changed their own way of thinking about research, these same participants were more positive regarding whether they had learned how to better communicate, collaborate, and identify other research worldviews (Figure 10).

Participant agreement ratings on items related to learning.

Figure 10. Agreement ratings on items related to Learning (n = 66)

Survey participants were also asked to rate the effectiveness of the Toolbox workshop on a scale ranging from zero (not effective at all) to 10 (most effective I can imagine). Once again, the responses were mixed; the average scores reflect a large degree of variance in the ratings. Table 2 summarizes the mean scores and variance for each item that was rated.

Table 2. Ratings of the effectiveness of aspects of the Toolbox related to Learning

Aspect of Toolbox	Mean Rating	Std. Dev.	N
As a way of learning how to communicate with others in a group.	5.58	2.70	55
As a way of learning how to work with a multidisciplinary group.	6.07	2.78	57
As a way of understanding how others work or conduct research.	6.25	2.66	56

Note: Scale range=0 (not effective) to 10 (most effective imaginable).

Respondents were asked several³ open-ended questions about the Toolbox learning experience. These examples provide some insight into the types of programmatic strengths and weaknesses that participants believe exist in the Toolbox workshop as a program for learning and professional development. It should be noted that two of the questions were not asked of all survey respondents, but only those who had indicated that their thinking about research had changed or that the Toolbox had helped their professional development, respectively. As a result, responses to these questions will likely be more useful in identifying examples of the causes of effective learning outcomes in these areas.

THINKING ABOUT RESEARCH

Seventeen of the 32 survey respondents who agreed that the Toolbox changed their thinking about research provided commentary as to how the workshop influenced their current thinking. Several individuals felt that the Toolbox provided them with a better understanding of the differences in research views which exists in various disciplines; giving them a new-found respect for the various points of view. In addition, respondents reported heightened awareness and thinking of the challenges specific to cross-disciplinary research and now feel more confident when communicating with researcher on collaborative projects. As one respondent stated, “I am more convinced that research is about mutual understanding, and to get there we need to talk about how we’re getting there.” A complete list of responses is provided in Appendix B.

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

There were 25 survey individuals who provided commentary regarding how the Toolbox workshop helped in their professional development. Overall, respondents felt that after attending the workshop they were better able to communicate with and understand individuals with differing research views. In addition, respondents indicated an increase in confidence when working with others in different disciplines. They believed the Toolbox workshop increased their ability to be more compassionate, active listeners, and increased their ability to be more productive in their collaborative efforts. Respondents also felt the Toolbox highlighted their own research views as well as encouraged them to conduct and seek out more cross-disciplinary research and opportunities. A complete listing of responses is provided in Appendix C.

³ The number asked per respondent varied based on the response to other questions. Only individuals who rated the professional development experience as positive to their professional development were asked an open-ended question about why.

EXPECTATIONS FOR LEARNING

The final question addressed whether the Toolbox met expectations regarding learning new concepts. While a majority of respondents did not have any pre-workshop expectations, those that did felt the Toolbox workshop met those expectations by providing exposure to different perspectives concerning research. In addition, respondents felt that the workshop provided a structured way of learning new concepts and skills and how to transfer them into practical use. Furthermore, they felt that the Toolbox raised their awareness of working through challenges faced and the importance of cross-disciplinary research. A complete listing of responses is provided in Appendix D.

BEHAVIOR

The survey included five items that address the behavior of TDI participants after the workshop. Survey items included agreement-rating questions addressing post-workshop behaviors, as well as multipart questions that ask about participants' engagement in collaborations with others. In general, responses to these behavioral questions were mixed, suggesting that while many respondents were impacted by the Toolbox experience, a sizeable minority have not engaged in behaviors that are indicative of impact.

The first questions about post-Toolbox behaviors focused on whether or not participants discussed topics or ideas from the workshop afterwards. It is expected that participants would be likely to talk about collaboration and research worldviews with colleagues if they had found the workshop to be an enlightening experience. As seen in Figure 11, around 60% of respondents agreed that they had discussed the Toolbox with both fellow attendees and other colleagues after attending. However, roughly 40% did not engage in post-Toolbox discussions about topics raised during the workshop sessions.

Post-Toolbox discussions: Since the Toolbox, I have discussed topics raised in the workshop with...

Figure 11. Agreement ratings regarding post-Toolbox discussions (n = 66)

Respondents were also asked about whether they had engaged in any new projects since the Toolbox workshop, either with members of their Toolbox group or other colleagues. If the respondent indicated “yes” they were then also asked to indicate how many new projects they had started and whether they had applied any lessons from their Toolbox workshop. Once again, the results were mixed. However, it does appear that respondents who started projects with individuals who were a part of the same Toolbox group generally rated the usefulness of the workshop to the project higher than those who worked with other individuals who had not attended their same workshop.

NEW PROJECTS STARTED WITH INDIVIDUALS WHO ATTENDED THE SAME TOOLBOX WORKSHOP

Only about one-quarter of respondents (18 out of 66) indicated that they had started a collaborative project with an individual who had also attended the same workshop. Of these 18 individuals, most (n=10) indicated that they had begun two collaborative projects since their Toolbox, with the rest indicating that they had either started only one new collaborative project (n=5) or that they had started five or more projects (n=3). When asked how effective the techniques or strategies learned during the workshop were for creating the team, a plurality (35%) indicated they were very effective, while only 12 percent indicated that the techniques or strategies were not effective at all (Figure 12).

Effectiveness of workshop for creating a team for a new project.

Figure 12. Rating of effectiveness of workshop for creating a team for a new project (n = 17).

NEW PROJECTS STARTED WITH OUTSIDE INDIVIDUALS

A larger portion of respondents, 65% (43 out of 66), indicated that since the Toolbox workshop they had started a collaborative project with individuals who had not attended their session. Collaborations with individuals who had not been part of the same workshop were also more prolific: most (58%) indicated that they had started at least three collaborative projects since their workshop. However, when asked whether they had been able to apply what they learned during the Toolbox workshop to the new projects, respondents were less enthusiastic. As shown in Figure 13, only about one-fourth of respondents indicated that they were able to use a great deal or a lot of what they had learned, compared to over half who responded that they were able to apply what they had learned by only a little or not at all.

Degree of application of Toolbox to new projects.

Figure 13. Responses to question regarding application of Toolbox to new projects (n = 39).

RESULTS

The results of participation in the Toolbox include the final outcomes that are desired for participants. These desired outcomes are tied to the Toolbox creators' belief that common understanding of research philosophies is a fundamental requirement for creating successful cross-disciplinary research (O'Rourke & Crowley, 2012). However, because defining and observing successful cross-disciplinary research on a large scale is not possible, the impact of the Toolbox must instead be gauged by its effectiveness as a training program and indicators traditionally associated with research activity.

Survey respondents were asked about two major aspects of traditional academic research output: research funding and research reporting. To help ensure that the questions apply beyond the university setting, the questions address alternate funding sources (e.g. business and contracts) and non-academic types of publications (e.g. technical reports, patents, etc.) in addition to traditional grants and journal publications. Overall, the responses to these questions indicate that Toolbox participants have been quite active in pursuing research funding and reporting on research results, however, most do not feel that their workshop experience had a strong impact on these activities.

RESEARCH FUNDING

Figure 14 shows the percent of survey respondents who indicated that they had applied for new sources of research funding since completing their workshop, along with the relative popularity of the types of funding that was sought. Over half of the respondents, 56% (36 out of 64 who completed this section of the survey), indicated that they had pursued at least one new source of research funding since finishing the Toolbox workshop. Grants remain by far the most popular type of research funding pursued, followed by internal funding, and other external sources. Of these 36 individuals, a majority (31 of 36) indicated that they had successfully obtained at least one new source of funding since completing the Toolbox workshop.

56% of participants pursued research funding.

Type of Funding

Figure 14. Pursuit of research funding since completing the Toolbox

The respondents who indicated that they had pursued new sources of research funding were also asked about the extent to which they were able to apply things learned during the workshop in order to collaborate in seeking new funding. The most popular responses were “a little” (33.3%) or “not at all” (30.6%). Only one respondent indicated that he/she was able to apply “a great deal” of what was learned in collaborating to obtain new funding. Unfortunately, this indicates that while former participants did pursue and obtain funding, lessons or ideas from the Toolbox did not play a strong role.

Degree of application of Toolbox to new projects.

Figure 15. Rating on applicability of the Toolbox in collaborating to obtain new funding (n = 36).

RESEARCH REPORTING AND PUBLICATIONS

The second Results area that participants were asked about is the authoring and distribution of research results. When asked whether they had authored (as lead or co-author) any type of publication or application (including patents or trademarks) since completing the Toolbox workshop, approximately 61% (39 of 64) responded in the affirmative. Nearly all of these individuals (38 of 39) indicated that one or more of these research publications had been done collaboratively. As seen in Figure 16, a substantial majority of respondents (90%) have collaboratively produced a written research report or other item since completing their Toolbox workshop.

32% of participants reported they have collaboratively written two items since the Toolbox workshop.

Figure 16. Number of products collaboratively written since completing your Toolbox experience (n=39).

Although former participants have been prolific in authoring research publications, they generally do not express positive views regarding the applicability of the Toolbox in collaborating on these publications. When asked about the applicability of the workshop to collaborating on these publications, the most popular response was “a little” to “not at all” (55%). On a positive note, 45% of respondents thought that applicability of Toolbox in authoring publications was “moderate” to “a great deal.”

Applicability of the Toolbox in collaborating to author research publications.

Figure 17. Rating of the applicability of the Toolbox in collaborating to author research publications (n = 38).

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions and recommendations reflect the evaluation team's assessment of TDI, based on the findings derived from the review of documents, survey of Toolbox participants, and discussions conducted with participants.

- 1. Variation in implementation and data collection make it difficult to assess TDI as a consistent intervention.** Our review of TDI data and documents found that, while the program has collected a lot of data and has a strong interest in data collection, there have been so many modifications to the data collection forms and modules that it currently prevents the examination of outcomes over time. This situation partially stems from TDI's interest in ongoing improvement and in customizing the program to the varying needs of its clients.
- 2. Most participants had a positive overall reaction to their workshop experience.** A majority of participants indicated that they enjoyed their workshop and that they felt it improved their communication and collaboration abilities. The comments of the interviewees also reflected overall positive experiences.
- 3. Participants who did not find the workshop to be valuable are a sizable minority.** On several measures of Reaction and Learning, the portion of respondents who selected negative or disagreement responses ranged above one-in-three, which represents a sizable share of participants. Areas of concern include the impact of the workshops on attitudes toward collaboration and communication, as well as the perception of the workshop as being a good use of time.
- 4. Former participants were divided as to whether or not TDI was an effective way of learning about communication and collaboration.** The ratings and comments left by survey respondents suggest that they found the Toolbox workshops to be an effective way of learning about the varied views and ideas about research. However, they were less consistent in their responses regarding whether or not they had learned about group communication and collaboration.
- 5. TDI is effective at generating discussion about research worldviews, even after the workshop session is complete.** Most participants indicated that they have had discussions about topics or ideas from their Toolbox session since completing the workshop.
- 6. The researchers who attend Toolbox workshops are engaged in collaborative research activities; however, most do not credit the Toolbox with impacting their research successes.** A majority of participants have gone after new funding, started new projects, and authored new reports during the period since their workshop. However, the portion of participants who indicated that they were able to apply a significant portion of what they learned during the Toolbox to their recent collaborative work was comparatively small.
- 7. Discussions with former participants suggest a desire for specific information on how to collaborate.** It was mentioned that a tool or information about how to deal with their own traits or beliefs, as well as the beliefs of others would be helpful in learning how to work with interdisciplinary teams.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORK AT TDI

Based on the observations and survey findings identified during the evaluation, we submit the following recommendations and suggestions for TDI's future work and study. These suggestions should be understood as ideas for consideration, and not empirically-based findings or conclusions.

1. If TDI chooses to pursue a long-term internal evaluation, **they should consider finalizing a consistent and limited set of modules and pre/post surveys to be used with all groups.** Additionally, maintaining the data within a single, relational database (e.g. MS Access) would allow for easier assessment of individual level outcomes over time.
2. To enhance the learning of Toolbox participants, **TDI could consider adding specific skill-development or knowledge-building components to the curriculum,** in addition to the broader discussion of research worldviews.
3. **Impact might be improved by increasing the level of engagement with individual participants.** The low response rate to the survey and request for interviews, combined with several comments about “not recalling” the Toolbox workshop, suggest that the experience was not memorable for many participants. Possible approaches include further study of the individual needs of prospective participants, developing additional materials on research worldview and collaboration that participants can take with them, and engaging in regular direct communication with individual participants to follow-up with participants after the workshops.
4. **Be aware of potential issues related to inter-generational conflict and individuals who may dominate conversation.** A small portion of respondents indicated that they found the workshop was not welcoming environment for expressing their views.

REFERENCES

- Crow, M. (2010). Organizing teaching and research to address the grand challenges of sustainable development. *BioScience*, 60(7), 488–489.
- Eigenbrode, S. D., O'Rourke, M., Althoff, D., Goldberg, C., Merrill, K., Morse, W., et al. (2007). Employing philosophical dialogue in collaborative science. *BioScience*, 57, 55–64.
- Kirkpatrick, D.L. & Kirkpatrick, J.D. (2006). *Evaluating Training Programs* (3rd Ed.). San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers, Inc.
- OECD. (1998). *Interdisciplinarity in Science and Technology*, Directorate for Science, Technology and Industry, OECD, Paris.
- O'Rourke, M. & Crowley, S.J. (2013). Philosophical intervention and cross disciplinary science: The story of the Toolbox project. *Synthese*, 190(11), 1937-1954
- Royal Society. (1996). *Inter-disciplinarity - Transport and the Environment*, London.
- Winowiecki, L., Smukler, S., Shirley, K., Remans, R., Peltier, G., Lothes, E., et al. (2011). Tools for enhancing interdisciplinary communication. *Sustainability: Science, Practice, and Policy*, 7(1), 74–80.

APPENDIX A

MSU TOOLBOX DIALOGUE WORKSHOP EVALUATION SURVEY

(Note that the format of the survey has been changed substantially from the electronic format for presentation in the print appendix. Survey branching was used so that some questions were only asked if prior responses indicated that they would be relevant to the respondent. The text below also excludes graphics and features such as response prompts and rules determining the number of responses allowed, e.g., select one or select all that apply.)

- 1) About how long ago did you participate in a Toolbox workshop? (Please select your best guess. If you have attended more than one Toolbox, please answer for the most recent one.)
 - Within the last 6 months
 - Between 6 and 12 months ago
 - Between one and two years ago
 - Between two and three years ago
 - Three or more years ago

- 2) Please indicate your agreement with each of the following statements based on your experience and satisfaction with the Toolbox workshop. As a reminder, you should have begun the Toolbox workshop by completing a survey instrument that had prompts on topics such as Motivation, Methodology, Application, Values, Communication, and Trust. Please respond to the following questions to the best of your knowledge.

(Scale: Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree)

 - The Toolbox prompts were effective conversation starters
 - The Toolbox workshop helped me identify some of my research worldviews
 - Overall, I enjoyed the Toolbox workshop
 - Attending the Toolbox workshop was a good use of my time

- 3) The following statements address the knowledge, skills, and attitudes acquired through participation in the Toolbox workshop. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.
 - I have a better understanding of how others in my group think about research and projects
 - The Toolbox workshop improved my attitude toward team communication
 - The Toolbox workshop helped our group identify some differing research worldviews
 - The Toolbox workshop helped to enhance collaboration among my group members

- 4) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your experience during the Toolbox workshop.

- Most people in my group contributed to the dialogue
 - Our conversation was an open exchange of thoughts and ideas
 - I felt free to present a view that differed from others in my group
 - My group's discussion addressed issues that I personally wanted to discuss
 - The Toolbox workshop helped build a sense of community among my group
- 5) Did your team participate in a group activity after the dialogue portion of the workshop?
- Yes
 - No
 - I do not recall
- 6) If answered yes, Indicate your level of agreement with each statement about the group activity.
- (Scale: Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree)*
- The activity improved communication in my group
 - The activity improved collaboration in my group
 - The activity was a good use of time
- 7) Please indicate the level of your agreement with the following statements, which focus on your work and research experiences since completing the Toolbox sessions.
- Since the Toolbox workshop, my own way of thinking about research has changed
 - Since the Toolbox workshop, I have discussed topics raised in the workshop with others who attended the session with me
 - Since the Toolbox workshop, I have discussed topics raised in the workshop with people who did not attend the Toolbox with me
 - I now have a better idea about how to communicate with individuals from different fields or disciplines
 - Because of the Toolbox, I am better able to identify the research worldviews that are expressed by other people
 - I now feel more capable of collaborating with individuals from different fields
 - Participating in the Toolbox helped my professional development
 - I have recommended the Toolbox workshop to others
- 8) What are one or two insights that you gained from the Toolbox workshop experience?
(Open-ended question)
- 9) You indicated that your thinking about research has changed? Can you tell us how or what has changed? (open-ended question)
- 10) You indicated that the Toolbox helped your professional development. Can you tell us how it helped? (Open-ended question)
- 11) Since the Toolbox, have you started any new collaborative projects with individuals who were in your Toolbox group (i.e. the team that you attended the Toolbox with)?

- Yes
- No

12) Approximately how many projects have you started with individuals from your Toolbox group since your Toolbox workshop experience?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 or more

13) How effective were the techniques/strategies learned during your Toolbox workshop for creating a team for the new project(s)?

- Extremely effective
- Very effective
- Moderately effective
- Slightly effective
- Not effective at all

14) Since the Toolbox, have you started any new collaborative projects with any individuals who did not attend the Toolbox session with you?

- Yes
- No

15) Approximately how many projects have you started with individuals who were not part of your Toolbox group since your Toolbox workshop experience?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 or more

16) To what extent were you able to apply what you learned during your Toolbox to these new research projects?

- A great deal
- A lot
- A moderate amount
- A little
- Not at all

17) Have you applied for financial support (e.g. a grant or research funding) or new business since completing your Toolbox? (select all that apply)

- Yes, grants
- Yes, other external research funding (e.g. contracts, private support, etc.)
- Yes, internal funding (i.e. support from my company, department, university, etc.)
- Yes, submitted a proposal for new business or new contracts
- Yes, sought new funds/business another way
- No

18) Approximately how many new sources of funding (i.e. grants, contracts, sales or new clients) have you obtained since your Toolbox workshop experience?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 or more

19) To what extent were you able to apply what you learned during your Toolbox in collaborating to obtain new funding?

- A great deal
- A lot
- A moderate amount
- A little
- Not at all

20) Have you authored or co-authored any reports, papers, and articles, or produced any other types of publications or applications (e.g. patents, trademarks, etc.) since completing your Toolbox workshop group?

- Yes
- No

21) How many items have you collaboratively written since your Toolbox experience?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 or more

22) To what extent were you able to apply what you learned during your Toolbox in collaborating to author these items?

- A great deal
- A lot
- A moderate amount
- A little
- Not at all

23) Thinking back, provide an overall rating on each aspect of your Toolbox experience. (0=not at all effective to 10=the most effective I can imagine) How effective was your Toolbox...

- As a way of learning how to communicate with others in a group.
- As a way of learning how to work with a multidisciplinary group.
- As a way of understanding how others work or conduct research.

24) Did the Toolbox meet your expectations for learning new concepts or skills? Why or why not? (Open-ended question)

Demographics

25) What is your primary professional role? (pick the one that best fits)

- Academic (faculty/professor)
- Scientist or researcher (for a private organization or at a university)
- Administration (e.g. manager, President/CEO, department chair, etc.)
- Student
- Other (please describe)

26) What is your primary work or research environment? (please select the one that best fits)

- Business / private industry
- Non-profit organization
- College or university (public or private)
- A K-12 school
- Government agency (local, state, or federal)
- Other

27) What age group are you in?

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 - 84
- 85 or older

28) What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Not listed

29) What is your race/ethnicity? (select all that apply)

- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Black or African American
- Hispanic/Latino
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
- White
- Other

30) Is there anything you would like to share about your Toolbox workshop experience?
(Open-ended question)

APPENDIX B

THINKING ABOUT RESEARCH

Q: You indicated that your thinking about research has changed? Can you tell us how or what has changed?

Better understanding

Better way to collect information

I am more aware of assumptions that others may have about research questions, methods, and results, and I am prepared to ask questions about that.

I am more convinced that research is about mutual understanding, and to get there, we need to talk about how we're getting there.

I have a deeper understanding of the range of world views beyond western thinking and science and a better understanding of those differences as part of the opportunity interdisciplinary work provides

I have encouraged my own institution to adopt this method in lieu of citi online training quizzes

I have more confidence to talk about research and collaborate with researchers in fields outside of the natural sciences (my research area). I would say more confidence than most of my peers.

I have since developed a professional interest in collaborative problem formulation

I realized that it's okay to make mistakes, because scientists (and science) are allowed to correct themselves later on without prejudice.

I think the biggest change came in the opportunity to now see differing points of view and respect them even if I disagree. My research is part of a bigger collaborative - a conversation building all members.

I'm less naive about some of the challenges and barriers to interdisciplinary research

I've done very successful collaboration with wide disciplinary crosses throughout my career. It has made me more tolerant of "hanging in there" waiting for things to come together, even though over the course of my career I've had more unsuccessful collaborations than successful ones. The workshop helped me see how I might waste a bit less time on things that are never going to pan out.

It's made me more open to alternative interpretations of rather basic things.

N/A

now able to think outside the world of engineering

There are multiple ways to research an issue and there isn't one right way or wrong way

Understanding that the worldviews and opinions of other researchers can vary widely. I knew that other researchers held different opinions but this was the only time when different opinions were all expressed. This has helped me understand and communicate with researchers on collaborative projects

Well, the scientific values are important; and my mom, who is a scientist, agreed 100% they were the big ones. And they are important to me. But I was never in it for curiosity and I forget the other; I was in it to change the world. The workshops really emphasized integrity, which is good; but no one ever asks, what are the implications of what I'm doing and finding? What will people do with it? Is this a thing we should be doing? And no one in my workshop seemed interested in that either. But that I what I think is interesting and important, so I left research and work in non-profits now.

APPENDIX C

TOOLBOX & PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Q: You indicated that the Toolbox helped your professional development. Can you tell us how it helped?

A better understanding of how people from other disciplines think about, frame, and attack problems

Better interaction with community

By opening doors for further involvement in the field. I am seen as a compassionate listener and a collaborative thinker - both are assets for my work.

Helped me realize the extent to which i can monopolize an otherwise collaborative process

Helped me to understand different perspectives on various topics

I am better prepared to begin interdisciplinary conversation and know where the landmines are located.

I do research on mutual understanding, so this gave me ideas of how to collect data.

I feel like I am better prepared to conduct interdisciplinary work. I feel more competent to handle conflicts and communication issues that may arise in that context.

I was able to collaborate with researchers which lead to a publication and workshop presentation

Increased confidence in working across disciplines

It allowed me to hear other's views and learn what to expect in the spectrum of NGO workers I may encounter in my career.

It contributed to the development of my communication skills, particularly in diverse group settings and inter-disciplinary research groups.

It gave me some confidence that I could be a contributing member to the group and that everyone has gaps in their knowledge, that is the point of forming a group.

It has helped me have productive collaborations across disciplines by making me comfortable with what I don't know and more willing to ask and probe about what others bring to a project.

it helped me better articulate the similarities between my own discipline (history) and its research methods and those of natural and social scientists

It helped me seek out interdisciplinary learning and research opportunities while in grad school that will make me be competitive for interdisciplinary post doc or job opportunities in the future.

It is give me additional practice and comfort with interdisciplinary research

It made it easier to talk about different topics with my peers.

It opened me to working with others outside my department. I now have new tools for reaching out to others.

It provided the required beacon training necessary to continue my work in that program

It reminded me that you can have productive dialogue even when coming at situations from differing points of view. In today's very polarized environment that is a very good thing

More open to and understanding of other people's viewpoints

Provided me with an approach for considering different world views and experience in a project.

The Toolbox is a good stepping-off place for dialogue. Unfortunately, several of the scenarios that I've experienced it in just moved on afterwards.

Toolbox me better able to understand that a group can have the same wishes for outcomes however very different ways to approach the solution as well as very different views on the usefulness of different means to an end based on individual life experience.

APPENDIX C cont.

Well maybe I fudged a bit on that answer. I'm so long in the tooth that "helping my professional development" usually just means reminding me where I left my glasses. I was thinking of the points I've already explained in other answers.

While I feel I had a good understanding of my project collaborators (and a good ability to learn where I didn't understand), it gave me a broader understanding of potential issues beyond the current project.

APPENDIX D

EXPECTATIONS FOR LEARNING

Q: Did the Toolbox meet your expectations for learning new concepts or skills? Why or why not?

Again, same complaint. That was interesting. Lets move on...

As someone who had already worked in numerous collaborative projects, the effect on my own thinking was incremental at best, but the workshop was effective in bringing together the project team as a whole.

Better. More responsive to participants

I did not come in with expectations.

I didn't have many expectations, but found this to be useful and pretty effective

I didn't see it as a way to learn new concepts or skills; more just sharing worldviews

I expected it facilitate more talking points and be more guided than it was.

I had no expectations

I had no such expectations, so no. Also, it was a lot more talking than it was understanding and applying new concepts or skills.

I think it was very useful at the time. Now I've forgotten most of what we discussed in the Toolbox session.

I was in a condensed version of the Toolbox so we did not have enough time to get into the depth of the different views.

I wasn't sure what to expect, so I can't say whether it met my expectations or not

I would not say the Toolbox itself accomplished that, but in raising awareness of the basis for issues that cropped up later and making me more intentional about working through those issues, The Toolbox in combination with team research was effective.

I'd have to say no b/c I have no sense that I'm using the methods today

I'm not sure; it met my requirement for something, scientific ethics training, maybe?

It was too short to do anything other than broach an idea. It was good, but I need more exposure to ideas to more effectively understand them.

No, since it was not effective enough to remember so many years later

No, this was a forced waste of time meant for middle schoolers not scientists.

No. I did not feel that the questions or discussion topics were relevant for our collaboration.

No. I think the groups were too large and conversations weren't structured in a particularly effective way. There was also a lot of confusion from participants as to what we were doing and why. As a result of these things, I think the engagement level isn't as high as it could have been.

The workshop exceeded my expectations. I repeat: I came to this workshop having more than \$5 million in career grants on projects that combine biology, engineering, social science and humanities scholarship. As a result of this work, I have published in the journals of more than a dozen different disciplines. I was not someone who had to be coaxed into the idea of collaboration, and frankly, I think I still know some stuff that could help the Toolbox. So I was supportive and curious, but not necessarily expecting to be overwhelmed with some newfound interest in or ability to do collaborative work. I was nonetheless impressed by the effectiveness of the workshop at revealing to all of us the sense that this project was not going to take off.

Yes

APPENDIX D cont.

Yes this workshop met my expectations. Taught me that multidisciplinary communication is essential

Yes, because it made me think about things in a new way.

Yes, especially in how to open up discussion with others about their research world view and then communicating how these lead to different expectations, research questions, products, etc.

Yes, it allowed me to explore others perspectives about research

Yes, it provided a structured way of learning about others as well myself.

Yes, it was very helpful.

Yes, particularly with regards to working in inter-disciplinary groups and making sure everyone has a voice.

Yes. I liked that these concepts and skills were taught and transferred in a very practical fashion.

APPENDIX E

INSIGHTS

Q: What are one or two insights that you gained from the Toolbox workshop experience?

This process helps to get around assumptions that might be made among collaborators regarding research worldviews.

Be aware of traditional practices of those in other fields. Be open to new ideas.

Differing conceptions of "science"

Establish a common vernacular is critical.

I didn't really gain any substantive insights. I already knew my views about research and the structure of my cognitive modeling of research, and the Toolbox workshop didn't change them. I did have two prior insights bolstered by the experience: 1. many young scientists don't know much about the structure and philosophical underpinnings of science and 2. in any group, the most extroverted will dominate to the detriment of the rest.

I learned that setting aside time for reflection near the END of a project helped us grow a lot!

I recall at the time that there were some good principles, but reading your list of questions makes me realize I retained very little from the session.

I remember really thinking deeply about the social status of all living things I also enjoyed the deeper insights into my teams thinking.

I'm sorry, this was so long ago. I don't remember precisely what we did or talked about.

I've done several of them, but each time I've had a sort of startling realization about how some things can be interpreted differently than I see them.

It is a good and effective tool

It made some of the attitudes and actions that pose challenges and barriers to interdisciplinary and large academic projects more clear to me. In particular, I recall a large group discussion where some senior scientists presented somewhat narrow and traditional disciplinary views early on which I think stunted the conversation and discouraged some of the younger and more inexperienced folks in the room from speaking up. This is something I see not infrequently as a young scientist and while I think it is important for younger scientists to challenge ideas and I recognize that senior folks are probably not trying to actively discourage participation formats and situations such as this can put certain individuals at a disadvantage and stifle creativity and innovation.

It was a long time ago! I remember getting a sense of the vocabulary of our interdisciplinary collaborators...

It was surprising how different research world views can be within one group. I think that insight helped me think more often about how others are perceiving and conceptualizing the research and, given that, how to communicate better with them.

Mainly that not all scientists think about science the way I do. Of course, opinions on science-related topics are far more varied among non-scientists.

Many of the differences are subtle and while they may not come out during a Toolbox dialogue, when they arise during the subsequent team research, thinking back to the Toolbox helps in recognizing and navigating them

Natural scientists hunt for commonalities across systems, while social scientists start with the assumption that there are not generalities and all systems are unique. Or, something, close to that.

APPENDIX E cont.

Not to be concerned about sharing my view and that it is better to ask for clarification about someone else's perspective than to make assumptions.

Nothing. This was a forced study for our group as part of our research internships. It didn't provide any insights as we all knew that people have different opinions and "collaborating" aka working together is something everyone has done since middle and high school.

Our workshop essentially told us that our group was probably not going to come together to work collaboratively. The questions in this survey seem to imply that this was not the desired outcome, but one thing I learned it is that is just as valuable to find out that your potential for collaboration is low as it is to improve group coherence.

That all research follows the same basic steps, no matter the content of the discipline

That community members will have difference of ideas but through open communication we can find a neutral point

That it is essential to discuss epistemological issues and scholarly commitments (i.e. professional codes of ethics, commitments to social justice, value placed on different research methodologies and theoretical frameworks) before agreeing to work on a project and write the proposal. Often these issues/differences come up in proposal writing stage, but not always. As a collaborator, I find working across these differences is very challenging.

That researchers in general don't have the same ethical outlook I do; the toolbox actually helped me leave research for that reason.

The need to understand others when collaborating different individuals may view the same topic differently, need to come to an agreement

The toolbox identified our differences but made no effort to bridge those differences.

This was so long ago I forgot I even did it, why am I getting emails about it now.

Toolbox workshop questions are too generic, not applicable to all research collaborations

Where my discipline and skill set fits in, what it can contribute

APPENDIX F

GENERAL COMMENTS ON THE WORKSHOP EXPERIENCE

Q: Is there anything you would like to share about your Toolbox workshop experience?

Cannot reiterate enough... great stepping-off place, but not well utilized moving forward in the group. I have already worked with almost everyone in my multi-disciplinary tool box group, so the conversation did not reveal anything new to me. Our group needed a deeper level of engagement than what the toolbox offered. The evening session and the introduction to the daytime workshop were very much the same, so I felt that the evening plenary was not a good use of my time.

DO NOT evaluate this tool solely in terms of its ability to generate and support collaborations. Killing unproductive collaborative efforts is every bit as important.

Great experience, and plan on repeating it with future Research groups

I enjoyed the group leaders from MSU. I thought they were very interesting and I appreciated their work. We were an unknowingly homogenous group- all working on the same team. I would be interested to see if the same experience would exist if the team were more diverse.

I think the benefits would be very particular to the project and participants. In my case, as PI for a new cross-disciplinary project, the experience itself was a good team building exercise, as opposed to transferring content that was unfamiliar.

I thought it was a divisive experience that focused on one world view of western academic science.

If there was some kind of follow up resource provided to follow up from this Toolbox event I have no recollection. There may be some great skills that I could have been using but they were not immediately evident and now any such memory has been lost. I think a resource portal and reminder prompts to use it (or something like this) would have improved my chances to put this into practice.

If you want effective feedback send this kind of survey sooner after a person participates.

It felt enriching and encouraging to have the toolbox session as we ventured into our interdisciplinary project. However, the time that has passed since then makes it difficult to remember what it was we were all jazzed about at the time. Should have ask us earlier!

It was a nice experience

It was a wonderful experience that has helped me in many ways.

It was incredibly useful and further solidified the relationships and cross-disciplinary understanding established in [my graduate school program]. I used this experience along with others to apply and get accepted to another program, where I recommended the Toolbox workshop to my PIs.

Keep it going!

Keep up the great work

APPENDIX F cont.

Please work to find ways to restrain the more obnoxious from dominating discussions. I have come to hate and have extreme anxiety about group settings because of them. As an introvert, I have had enough time speaking up in a group without having to worry about being shot down immediately if I disagree with the dominant personality. I largely remained silent during at least one Toolbox workshop because of the problem. Speaking is hard enough. What is the point if one is not going to be listened to? Beyond this, the Toolbox workshops, for all their virtues, are insufficient. There is a deep lack of knowledge of the nature and proper practice of science among young scientists, and an occasional workshop is not going to correct the problem. There needs to be a comprehensive reform of scientific training if the problem is going to be tackled in an effective manner.

WESTERN MICHIGAN UNIVERSITY

Evaluation Center

Authors:

Brad R. Watts

Stephanie N. Means

Emma Perk

This 2017 evaluation report was created for the MSU Toolbox Dialogue Initiative program, for questions regarding this report, contact Dr. Watts, Assistant Director, Evaluation Center, Western Michigan University (brad.r.watts@wmich.edu).